

Benz_10perc_1218

Sample Name **Benz_10perc_1218**
Date collected **2025-12-18**

Pulse sequence **PROTON**
Solvent **d2o**

Temperature **28.5**
Spectrometer **varian300.chem.byu.edu-inova300**
Study owner **marsh81**

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SAMPLE		wet		n
date	Dec 18 2025	SPECIAL		
solvent	d2o			
file	/opt/nmrdata/mars	temp		28.5
h81/Benz_10perc_1218_20		gain		30
251218_01/PROTON_02.fid		spin		0
		hst		0.008
		pw90		11.500
ACQUISITION		alfa		10.000
sw	4799.6	FLAGS		
at	3.414			
np	32768	il		n
fb	3000	in		nw
bs	32	dp		y
ss	4	hs		nn
d1	20.000	PROCESSING		
nt	8			
ct	8	lb		0.50
TRANSMITTER		fn		131072
tn	H1	DISPLAY		
sfrq	299.972	sp		-599.9
tof	300.0	wp		4799.5
tpwr	56	rfl		600.0
pw	3.833	rfp		0
DECOUPLER		rp		-36.2
		lp		-41.2
dn	C13	PLOT		
dof	0			
dm	nnn	wc		234
decwave	W40_pfgAuSW	sc		8
dpwr	28	vs		2133
dmf	26316	th		44
PRESATURATION		ai	cdc	ph
satmode	n			
	Plotname: PROTON_02_plot04--			